

Signs of local adaptation and phenotypic plastic response to elevation shifted between light and shade in Snapdragon plants

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Multiple environmental drivers can shape the plastic and microevolutionary adaptive responses of plants. Yet, experimental studies on local adaptation and phenotypic plasticity rarely investigate how different dimensions of local environments might interact and modify the signature patterns of these mechanisms. In common garden experiments, adaptive signatures are usually investigated under full-light conditions. Here, we tested whether the potential adaptive signature to elevation recorded in an open habitat was maintained when the experiment was replicated onsite under the shade of vegetation. This was done in two snapdragon plant subspecies (*Antirrhinum majus striatum* and *A. m. pseudomajus*) by using common garden experiments at different elevations. The population genetic divergence in germination-related traits was suggestive of a pattern of local adaptation to elevation under regular sunlight in *A. m. striatum*, but not in *A. m. pseudomajus*. In understory shade, these phenotypic patterns were different and suggested maladaptive or neutral responses to elevation in both subspecies. Overall, the magnitude of plastic responses was stronger than trait genetic divergence. Our findings imply that caution should be taken when extrapolating the evolutionary significance of these patterns because they are not stable from one local environmental condition to the next. They also imply that selection mechanisms linked to germination vary across heterogeneous environments in snapdragon plants. Forecasting the ability of plants to adapt to environmental changes based on common garden and reciprocal transplant experiments must account for the multivariate nature of the environment.

Altitudinal gradient | *Antirrhinum majus* | local adaptation | quantitative genetics | phenotypic plasticity | shade-induced plasticity | subspecies divergence

1. Introduction

Local adaptation and adaptive phenotypic plasticity are widely recognised as important mechanisms allowing species to cope with ongoing climate change (Jump & Penuelas, 2005; Hoffmann & Sgrò, 2011; Franks *et al.*, 2014; Kelly, 2019). Local adaptation is the microevolutionary response to local selection that makes populations fitter in their own local habitat than any other populations (Kawecki & Ebert, 2004). Evidence for past microevolutionary responses to selection caused by climate differences does not necessarily indicate that adaptation to climate change will occur (Jump & Penuelas, 2005; Valladares *et al.*, 2014), but provides basic information about adaptive mechanisms that shape the standing genetic variation found among populations for climate-related responses. This information can in turn help building scenarios of species adaptation to climate change. Obtaining this information in plants is usually done by conducting experimental approaches where phenotypic traits are compared between populations from different local environments. These environments are highly complex and multidimensional, and are generally simplified to be studied. Whether this experimental simplification of population local environments can alter our extrapolation of adaptive scenarios remains how-

ever poorly tested (but see Anderson & Wadgymar, 2019).

Phenotypic plasticity refers to the ability of the phenotype for a given genotype to change in response to environmental conditions (Bradshaw, 1965). Trait plasticity can be adaptive or maladaptive in relation to a plant fitness (Ghalambor *et al.*, 2007, 2015). Adaptive plasticity is widely recognised as a mechanism that can allow plants to track rapid shifts in phenotypic optima, thereby increasing the likelihood of populations persistence under environmental changes. Identifying adaptive plasticity to contrasted climatic conditions can therefore help predicting the ability of populations to persist to ongoing and future climate changes (Kelly, 2019). Today, adaptive plasticity and local adaptation are well documented. A lot of research is now directed towards understanding their relative roles. The plasticity of a trait can change in different environments so that plasticity itself can be considered to be plastic (Roubeau Dumont *et al.*, 2019). The multidimensional

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46 complexity of the natural environment that organisms live
47 in can affect in complex ways the phenotypic expression of
48 traits (Morel-Journel *et al.*, 2020). Whether the adaptive
49 significance of plasticity and therefore its interaction
50 with local adaptation can be extrapolated on the basis
51 of experiments might therefore rely on the set of en-
52 vironmental local conditions used in the given experiment.
53

54 Elevation gradients have long been used to assess
55 climate related signatures of adaptation (Halbritter *et al.*,
56 2018). Several environmental factors vary along elevation
57 gradients (e.g., temperature, humidity, air pressure, vege-
58 tation cover, see Körner 2003). Most studies comparing
59 the effect of elevation on plant populations cultivated
60 in common gardens and reciprocal transplants do not
61 decompose the effects of onsite environmental drivers
62 because experimental settings can only incorporate
63 a limited number of environmental treatments. For
64 instance, most - if not all - studies testing for local
65 adaptation to elevation are carried out in full light. Yet
66 many plant species growing along elevation gradients are
67 not alpine (i.e. occurring exclusively above tree line)
68 and are therefore likely to live in heterogeneous light
69 environments. Shade provided by the vegetation cover
70 can vary between and within populations independently
71 from elevation. Whether replicating the experiment
72 at a similar elevation, even in a similar location, but
73 in a different environmental condition (e.g., in the full
74 light of an open habitat vs under the shade provided
75 by vegetation) might affect trait values, results and
76 conclusions on adaptive mechanisms is rarely tested
77 (but see Anderson & Wadgyman 2019 for an example
78 of disrupted local adaptation to elevation caused by
79 snow removal treatments). As a consequence, our
80 understanding of plant adaptation to elevation might be
81 biased because we oversimplify the local environment of
82 wild populations in reciprocal transplant and common
83 garden experiments (Chevin & Lande, 2015; Westneat
84 *et al.*, 2019). Since this information is also used to forecast
85 population responses to climate change, extrapolated
86 scenarios from these approaches might also be incorrect.
87

88 Local adaptation can result from natural selection
89 acting at any plant life stages, but the majority of studies
90 do not track plant over their entire life-cycle and focus
91 on late life-history stages (e.g. juveniles or young adults,
92 Gibson *et al.* 2016). Yet, selection can be particularly
93 severe, and organisms often suffer high mortality
94 rates at early life stages (Hamilton, 1966; Caswell &
95 Salguero-Gómez, 2013). In addition, selection on early
96 life stages has cascading effects and can influence how
97 evolution shapes the diversity of subsequent life stages
98 (Donohue, 2014). For instance, the timing of germination
99 influences the seasonal environment experienced by adult
100 plants (Donohue, 2002; Donohue *et al.*, 2005). Field
101 studies have shown that germination timing is subject

102 to strong natural selection in a wide range of plant
103 species (Donohue *et al.*, 2010). As a result, there is a
104 growing interest for studying possible adaptive signatures
105 detected at the seed and germination stages (Donohue,
106 2014; Postma & Ågren, 2016; Gibson *et al.*, 2016).
107

108 Here, we tested for the reproducibility of the potential
109 signature of local adaptation and plasticity in response
110 to elevation between two local environmental conditions:
111 open habitat and understory. One originality of our pro-
112 tocol is to use seed from similar families to replicate the
113 same gene pool in different treatments (elevation x light
114 treatment). This test was achieved by conducting two
115 common garden experiments at high and low-elevation in
116 snapdragon plants (*Antirrhinum majus*). This species
117 occurs naturally in heterogeneous light habitats ranging
118 from sea level to a 1800 m elevation just below tree-line.
119 We focus on two germination-related traits widely
120 recognised for their role in plant adaptation (Donohue
121 *et al.*, 2010): the seed germination rate, and the timing
122 of seed germination. We reproduced this approach in the
123 two parapatric yet genetically closely related subspecies
124 (*A. m. ssp. striatum* and *ssp. pseudomajus*) that inhabit
125 closely similar ecological niches in the south of France.
126

127 2. Material and methods

128 **Study system.** *Antirrhinum majus* L. (Plantaginaceae) is
129 a hermaphroditic, self-incompatible, short-lived perennial
130 species producing annual inflorescences with zygomorphic
131 flowers. It produces small seeds dispersed by gravity a
132 few metres apart from the plant when the fruit dehisces
133 (Andalo *et al.*, 2010; Khimoun *et al.*, 2011). Cultivated
134 *A. majus* horticultural varieties are known to have a poor
135 and slow rate of seed germination (Bhargava *et al.*, 2015).
136 Seeds germinate better on the surface of soil and at mild
137 temperature (around 20°C, Kang & Choi 2006). While
138 *A. majus* has been used as a model for developmental
139 genetics for more than 80 years (Schwarz-Sommer *et al.*,
140 2003), knowledge on the ecology of this species in wild
141 populations remains limited. There is no evidence for
142 a seed bank, and no informations about the longevity
143 of seeds in the soil, and their germination temporal
144 dynamics in wild populations. Recently some authors
145 formulated the hypothesis that *A. majus* has a persistent
146 seed bank with seeds able to survive longer than one
147 year but no evidence supporting this hypothesis is
148 available (unpublished data in Arathoon *et al.* 2020). It
149 is reasonable to expect that most seeds remain viable
150 in the soil until they have an opportunity to germinate
151 in spring of the following year. This is coherent with results
152 from studies on cultivated *A. majus* which generally
153 present a unique peak of germination (Kang & Choi,
154 2006; Bhargava *et al.*, 2015). Geographic distribution
155 of *A. majus* in southern Europe is centred over the
156 Pyrenees Mountains (Khimoun *et al.*, 2013). It occurs

Fig. 1. Map of *A. majus* populations that were sampled across the geographic range of the species in Southern France. Pink dots represent *A. m. pseudomajus* populations, yellow dots represent *A. m. striatum* populations. Lercoul and ENSFEA are the locations of the common gardens. Elevation follows a continuous range with lowest elevation in white (<50m) and higher elevation in black (> 2500m).

157 from sea level to an altitude of 1900 m (Andalo *et al.*,
 158 2010), on limestone or siliceous substrates and in habitats
 159 with contrasted moisture regimes (rainfall 500-1000
 160 mm per year). *A. majus* thrives in disturbed habitats,
 161 and is especially common along roadside and railway
 162 embankments (Khimoun *et al.*, 2013). *A. majus* plants
 163 grow in a large variety of light environments, including
 164 fully open (e.g., scree), fully shaded (e.g., understory
 165 vegetation, dense grassland meadows), or heterogeneous
 166 (sparse shrubland) areas (Khimoun *et al.*, 2013).
 167

168 **The subspecies level.** *A. majus* plants harbour either
 169 magenta or yellow flowers, which can be used to
 170 distinguish between the two interfertile subspecies
 171 *A. m. pseudomajus* and *A. m. striatum* respectively
 172 (Andalo *et al.*, 2010). The two subspecies are distributed
 173 parapatrically and come into contact at their geographic
 174 range margins (Khimoun *et al.*, 2011). The geographic
 175 range of *A. m. striatum* is surrounded by the range of *A.*
 176 *m. pseudomajus* (Khimoun *et al.*, 2013). The transition
 177 between subspecies in the contact zones can occur over a

178 very short distance (<1 km) (Whibley, 2006).
 179 At the genetic level, 1% genetic differentiation was found
 180 between *A. m. pseudomajus* and *A. m. striatum* on the
 181 basis of putatively neutral microsatellite loci, which was
 182 one order of magnitude lower than the 10% differentiation
 183 found amongst populations (Pujol *et al.*, 2017). There
 184 is evidence for gene exchange between subspecies in
 185 multiple populations across contact zones (Khimoun
 186 *et al.*, 2011). Genome scans across a particular contact
 187 zone in the Pyrenees also revealed little to negligible
 188 differentiation between the two subspecies, with the
 189 exception of loci underlying flower colour differences
 190 between the two subspecies that were characterised by
 191 high differentiation (Whibley, 2006; Tavares *et al.*, 2018).
 192 At the environmental level, the separation between the
 193 geographic distribution of *A. m. pseudomajus* and *A.*
 194 *m. striatum* is not explained by habitat differences, as
 195 illustrated by the substantial overlap of environmental
 196 conditions between the two species (Khimoun *et al.*,
 197 2013). Phenotypic differentiation was found between
 198 these two subspecies in a Q_{ST} - F_{ST} approach conducted

199 in one common garden but it was very low (c.a. 2%,
200 excluding flower colour). The same approach however
201 suggested a pattern of local adaptation to elevation
202 across *A. m. striatum* populations, but not across *A. m.*
203 *pseudomajus* populations (Marin *et al.*, 2020).
204

205 **Populations and seed collection.** Fifteen wild popula-
206 tions of *A. majus* were sampled in 2011 from low and high
207 elevation habitats distributed across its native geographic
208 range (between north-eastern Spain and south-western
209 France, Fig 1). The studied populations covered most
210 of the altitudinal range of the species (0 m to 1600 m,
211 see Table S1 in Supporting Information). They have
212 been chosen based on i) their location spread across the
213 geographic range of the species, ii) their altitude to cover
214 the elevation range of the species that can be separated
215 in two strata (6-750 and 750-1800 meters) presenting
216 contrasted climate conditions (Marin *et al.*, 2020), and
217 iii) their within-population heterogeneity in vegetation
218 cover resulting in diverse light conditions. None of these
219 populations grows above tree lines. Populations from low
220 and high elevation habitats are confronted to contrasted
221 environmental conditions (Fig S1). For example, these
222 conditions ranged from 14.8°C and 52 mm (at BAN, 61
223 m above sea level) to 6.1°C and 94 mm (at MON, 1564 m
224 above sea level) based on fifty-year averages (1950-2000)
225 of mean annual temperature and average monthly rainfall
226 extracted from the WorldClim database (resolution 1
227 km², www.worldclim.org, Hijmans *et al.* 2005). We used
228 the same populations as in Marin *et al.* 2020, completed
229 by one population for *A. m. striatum* (VIL see, Fig 1).
230

231 Seed families used to produce the plants grown
232 in this experiment were not sampled directly in the
233 wild but produced by two successive generations of
234 parental plants that were germinated and grew in a
235 common garden environment (Fig S2). Only the first
236 parental generation of plants was germinated from seeds
237 collected from field populations. These two generations
238 of plants regenerated before our experiment are expected
239 to have reduced maternal environmental effects that
240 could have otherwise biased the trait values recorded
241 during the experiments presented here. They might
242 nevertheless have resulted in the preconditioning of
243 plants to this specific set of environmental conditions,
244 which would homogenise phenotypic difference between
245 populations and make the finding of local adaptation
246 more conservative. In each wild population, seeds were
247 sampled in October 2011 and randomly collected from
248 mature plants. Seeds sampled in the wild were sown in
249 spring 2012 in individual pots (9 × 9 × 10 cm) filled
250 with universal compost in a greenhouse at the CNRS
251 Experimental Ecology Station in Moulis, France. This
252 first generation of plants germinated and grew with no
253 nutrient addition under an average temperature from

15 to 28°C and weekly watering. Mature plants were
254 hand-pollinated during the summer 2012. Crosses were
255 conducted within populations where mates were assigned
256 randomly. The seeds produced by these crosses constitute
257 the 2012 collection of seed families. We sowed these
258 seed families in spring 2014 in a common garden at
259 ENSFEA (Toulouse, France). This second generation
260 of plants were germinated and grew in individual pots
261 (9 × 9 × 10 cm) filled with universal compost, with no
262 nutrient addition, under outdoor climatic conditions
263 (average month temperatures ranging from 20.6 to 21.5°C
264 and cumulative monthly rainfall ranging from 28.3 to
265 73.4 mm). Plants were supplied with water in case of
266 prolonged drought. Mature plants were hand-pollinated
267 during summer 2014. Crosses were conducted within
268 populations where mates were assigned randomly. The
269 seeds resulting from these crosses constitute the 2014
270 collection of seed families that were used in 2015 in the
271 experiments presented here.
272
273

274 **Common garden sites representing low and high**
275 **elevation conditions.** In our study, we were interested in
276 obtaining signature patterns reflecting partial evidence
277 that germination contributes to the local adaptation of
278 populations to elevation in order to test the stability of
279 such signal under full light and vegetation shade. This
280 signature patterns were obtained by using a “parallel”
281 approach as described by Kawecki & Ebert (2004);
282 several replicate populations originating from each
283 habitat type (e.g. low- vs high-elevation habitats) were
284 sampled and compared, here in terms of germination in
285 each habitat type (low- vs high-elevation gardens). If
286 germination contributes directly to the local adaptation
287 of populations to elevation, the populations originating
288 from high-elevation habitats should outperform the
289 populations originating from low-elevation habitats in the
290 high-elevation garden whereas the populations originating
291 from low-elevation habitats should outperform the
292 populations originating from high-elevation habitats in
293 the low-elevation garden. We therefore transplanted seeds
294 from every population in two sites (Fig S2). One site was
295 located at low elevation, in Toulouse, France (elevation
296 152 m). The other one was located at high elevation, in
297 the Siguer valley at Lercoul, France (elevation 1100 m;
298 see Fig 1). These two sites were chosen because their
299 climatic conditions were respectively representative of
300 the range of average climatic conditions experienced by
301 the populations sampled in the lowest half (from sea
302 level to 750 m) and highest half (from 750 m to 1800 m)
303 of the elevation range respectively. The site at higher
304 elevation received more rainfall, was cooler, and had a
305 less severe summer drought than the low-elevation site
306 (See supplementary information, Fig S1). Keeping in
307 mind that sites were chosen to represent elevations, one
308 limitation of our experiment is that the effects of site and

309 elevation were confounded. Although we homogenised
310 other environmental conditions (e.g., germination soil
311 substrate, root development available space) between
312 sites as to focus on climate differences between high and
313 low elevation, differences between elevations cannot be
314 attributed exclusively to elevation, and could also be
315 due to other site-specific uncontrolled environmental
316 conditions.

318 **Shade treatment: shaded by vegetation.** At each site,
319 two different common gardens were used to expose plants
320 to two different environmental conditions: full light in
321 an open habitat and shade provided by vegetation in
322 the understory. These common gardens were within 200
323 m of each other to keep the local climate conditions
324 that are not affected by shade as similar as possible.
325 We were interested in testing the reproducibility of
326 the signature of local adaptation to elevation, rather
327 than evaluating the role of light and shade in local
328 adaptation. We used natural vegetation to induce
329 a differential environmental condition based on the
330 presence and absence of shade. Therefore, along with this
331 “shade treatment” induced by vegetation, moisture and
332 biotic interactions were undoubtedly different between
333 treatments. These separate treatments (completely open
334 or completely shaded) mimic conditions experienced
335 by snapdragon plants in their native habitats where
336 individuals develop in heterogenous light conditions.
337 All the populations experienced both light and shade
338 environments in their native habitat, therefore we are
339 not expecting a differential adaptation to light between
340 populations. These two conditions (light and shade)
341 are known to induce plastic changes in the morphology
342 and germination in *A. majus* (Gourcilleau *et al.*, 2019;
343 Mousset *et al.*, 2020). We evaluated the contrast in light
344 conditions by measuring the photosynthetically active
345 radiation (PAR), which was significantly reduced under
346 shade (See supplementary information, Fig S3 and Fig
347 S4). Change in PAR is expected with elevation alongside
348 with temperature, rainfall etc. While some differences in
349 PAR occurred between high and low elevations in our
350 experiment, they were negligible in comparison to the
351 effect of shade (Fig S3).

353 **Experimental design in the common gardens.** We
354 sowed 5360 seeds in spring 2015. Seeds germinated and
355 plants grew outdoor in the gardens. In every garden, the
356 constitution of the 15 study populations was the same.
357 In every garden, seeds used for a given population came
358 from c. 14 seed families (between 13 and 15 depending
359 on the population). The same seed families were used in
360 every garden, so that the four gardens were composed by
361 a similar gene pool. In every garden, every seed family
362 was represented by six or seven individuals (Table S1,
363 Supporting Information). It is important to note that

our experimental setting was made to compare the effect
of elevation with a particular interest for contrasted
climate environmental conditions while homogenising
other potential effects (e.g., soil composition). Therefore,
seeds were sown on the top of individual pots (9 × 9
× 10 cm) with clay universal (TS3 Argile code 404,
Klasmann©) and compost universal (BP2 Kompact
code 294, Klasmann©). These pots were arranged
in a randomised design on a tarpaulin covered with
compost universal. Plants grew in pots filled with no
nutrient addition and under outdoor climatic conditions
in planting sites. Plants were supplied with water in case
of prolonged drought.

Germination-related traits and fitness optimum. Here,
we focused on two germination-related traits: the seed
germination rate, and the time to germination. In both
common gardens, the germination date was monitored
during the summer 2015 three times per week. To our
knowledge, no evidence for several peaks of germination
has been reported in *A. majus*. We therefore did not
consider that seeds that did not germinate the first year
harboured potential for germination in future years. As a
result, we also did not consider that seeds that did not
germinate the first year could play a role in a particular
ecological strategy of delayed germination across seasons.

Seed germination and time to germination are traits
of interest when considering the response of plants to
elevation. The seed germination is a direct measure of
plant survival; it is monotonically related to fitness (i.e.
under directional selection in all populations, and all
sites). The timing of seed germination is not a direct
measure of plant performance but it has a strong effect
on seedling survival: it influences seedling seasonal
exposure to potentially lethal environmental factors
and to advantageous conditions for subsequent growth
and reproduction (Donohue *et al.*, 2010). The timing
of seed germination is not monotonically related to
fitness. Optimal times to germination may differ in
different locations. Selection may favour either early or
delayed germination, depending on when environmental
conditions are advantageous or deleterious. Selection
for increased fecundity should favour early germination.
Indeed, plants germinating earlier can reach a larger
size before reproduction and reproduce over a longer
period (Hoyle *et al.*, 2015). At low elevation, selection
for increased fecundity and summer drought mortality are
expected to favour early germination. At high elevation,
two contrasted hypotheses can be drawn (Schütz, 2002).
Short growing seasons in sub-alpine habitats should
favour early germination, to provide enough time for
growth and reproduction. This is particularly true
for annual plants, but would be less advantageous for
short-lived perennial plants such as *A. majus*. On the

other hand, the high risk of seedling mortality due to adverse spring conditions may select for delayed germination. Studies on alpine environments suggest that there is no global alpine germination strategy (Körner, 2003; Giménez-Benavides *et al.*, 2005; Wagner & Simons, 2009; Hoyle *et al.*, 2015).

Seed germination and time to germination are also traits of interest when considering the response of plants to light and shade environments. As other small-seeded species, *A. majus* requires light to germinate (seeds germinate only on or near soil surface but not buried in the soil, Leishman *et al.* 2000; Milberg *et al.* 2000). Additionally, late germination might be expected under shade (Smith & Whitelam, 1997). Therefore, we expected a lower germination rate and delayed germination under shade than under light in all populations and in both subspecies.

Statistical analysis.

Estimating environmental, genetic and $G \times E$ interactions variances. For each subspecies, we used GLMMs (Generalised Linear Mixed Model) with fixed and random effects to quantify the magnitude of the environmental, genetic and genetic-by-environment ($G \times E$) interaction variances in the response of germination-related traits to site elevation and shade treatment. Fixed effects included the site elevation effect ($V_{Elevation}$), the shade treatment effect (V_{Shade}) and their interaction ($V_{Elevation \times Shade}$) effect on the phenotype. These fixed effects were therefore used to estimate environmental variances. For both traits, random effects were included to estimate the between-population variance (V_B), the between-family effect variance (V_F), and the population \times site elevation \times shade treatment interaction variance (V_{BXE}) and the family \times site elevation \times shade treatment (V_{FXE}) interaction variance. Both V_B and V_F refer to genetic effects, whereas V_{BXE} and V_{FXE} refers to components of the genetic by environment interaction (V_{GXE}). Phenotypic plasticity is estimated by environmental variances ($V_{Elevation}$, V_{Shade} , and $V_{Elevation \times Shade}$) and is also included in the genetic by environment interaction (Scheiner & Goodnight, 1984; Scheiner & Lyman, 1989). Since only a subset of individuals germinated, the analysis of the time to germination was conducted on a smaller dataset than the dataset for the germination rate. The error distribution was chosen to fit the residuals of each trait in the models: (i) a binomial model (with a logit link function) was used to analyse the germination success (0 vs 1), (ii) a Gaussian model was used to analyse the time to germination.

We established whether the phenotypic plasticity due to environmental effects (site elevation, shade treatment and interactions) explained significant variance in germination-related traits by comparing models with

and without the environmental effects on the basis of Likelihood Ratio Tests (LRT, Zuur *et al.* 2009).

Identifying patterns reflecting local adaptation to elevation.

The “local” elevation vs. “foreign” elevation criterion (Kawecki & Ebert, 2004) was chosen to analyse the local adaptation of populations to elevation on the basis of germination-related traits. We considered that we observed a potential signature of local adaptation to elevation if populations originating from high-elevation habitats had higher germination rates than populations from low-elevation habitats in the high-elevation site, whereas populations originating from low-elevation habitats had higher germination rates than populations from high-elevation habitats in the low-elevation site. The reaction norms (i.e. phenotypic responses of same genotypes between high and low elevation sites) of populations originating from high- and low-elevation habitats should logically be crossing in the presence of adaptation to elevation for germination success at high and low elevations. For the time to germination, the reaction norms should not be interpreted in the same way. As explained above, this trait is not directly and monotonically correlated with fitness. Therefore, crossing and non-crossing reaction norms can both reflect a pattern of local adaptation to elevation depending on the fitness advantage that a given trait value provides in a given habitat. For example, germinating later might provide an advantage in late spring conditions whereas germinating earlier might be advantageous when spring is early.

For each subspecies, we performed GLMMs with fixed and random effects that are closely similar to the models presented in the above section but differ to some extent to allow for specific hypotheses to be tested. The fixed effects included the site elevation effect, the shade treatment, the elevation of origin of the population (as a discrete variable, "high" vs "low"), and their interactions. The random effects included the between-population variance (V_B) and the between-family effect variance (V_F). The error distribution were similar to previous models. We established whether the elevation of origin explained significant variance in germination-related traits by comparing models with and without the elevation of origin on the basis of their LRT (Zuur *et al.*, 2009). Then, we tested the significance of the elevation of origin \times site elevation and the elevation of origin \times site elevation \times shade treatment interactions, which reflect the signature of local adaptation for the germination rate. For the time to germination, the significance of the site elevation effect and the site elevation \times shade treatment interaction can also reflect the signature of local adaptation. Finally, significant differences between populations originating from high and low elevation within each site, and significant differences between high

529 and low-elevation sites for the same populations were
530 evaluated by using Wilcoxon tests (non-parametric data).

531
532 All statistical analyses were performed using the
533 R.3.5.0 software (R Core Team, 2018). All generalised
534 mixed-model were implemented in R via the glmmTMB
535 R-package (Brooks *et al.*, 2017). Assumptions of
536 models (e.g. heteroscedasticity, over or under dispersion,
537 significance of outliers) were checked via the DHARMA
538 R-package (Hartig, 2020); only models for the time to
539 germination in *A. majus pseudomajus* violated uniformity
540 of residuals assumptions according to DHARMA. Caution
541 had been taken when considering the results of this model.

543 **Availability of code and data.** The code and data for
544 producing figures and results in this paper are available
545 on Zenodo.

547 3. Result

548 **Stronger phenotypic plasticity than genetic differenti-**
549 **ation among populations.** Phenotypic plasticity due to
550 environmental variance was found for both germination-
551 related traits, as illustrated by significant environmental
552 effects of the site elevation or shade treatment or site ele-
553 vation \times shade treatment interaction (Table 1). In both
554 subspecies, the site elevation \times shade treatment interac-
555 tion was statistically significant for both traits, meaning
556 the impact of elevation varied between light environments.

557
558 The models including phenotypic plasticity due to
559 environmental variance (site elevation, shade treatment
560 and interactions) explained the data better than the
561 model without phenotypic plasticity (LRT, Table 2).
562 This phenotypic plasticity explained approximately 10 to
563 21% of the variation in germination-related traits (see
564 marginal R^2 in Table 1). A non-negligible proportion
565 of variance was also explained by genetic variation as
566 demonstrated by conditional R^2 reaching 21 to 45% of
567 the variation (Table 1).

568
569 The largest component of genetic variation for
570 germination related-traits was the genetic variation of the
571 degree of plasticity ($G \times E$ interaction, Table 1), which
572 with environmental variance formed the phenotypic
573 plasticity. Genetic variation between populations and
574 between families within populations were smaller in both
575 subspecies. No or small variation in both germination
576 related-traits was found among populations for both
577 subspecies (Table 1). A larger proportion of variation
578 was explained by the within-population genetic variation
579 estimated by the family effect. A graphical representation
580 of average population phenotypic values is available in
581 the supplementary (Fig S5 and S6).

583 **Partial signatures of local adaptation to elevation**

584 **under light for *A. m. striatum*.** The models including the
585 elevation of origin fitted the data better than the null
586 models (i.e. models without the elevation of origin) for
587 all traits and all subspecies (Table 2). The significant
588 effects of the three-way interaction elevation of origin
589 \times site elevation \times shade treatment for the germination
590 rate, and the two-way interaction site elevation \times
591 shade treatment interaction for the time to germination
592 suggested a signature of local adaptation (Table 3). In *A.*
593 *m. striatum*, the “local” elevation vs. “foreign” elevation
594 criterion was partially satisfied under light conditions for
595 both the germination rate and the time to germination.
596 As expected, plants originating from high-elevation
597 habitats had a significantly higher germination rate
598 compared to plants originating from low-elevation
599 habitats, in the high-elevation site under light condition
600 (Fig 2 a). Yet, in the low-elevation site, differences
601 in germination success were not significant between
602 populations from high and low-elevation habitats (Fig 2
603 a). Therefore the “local” vs. “foreign” criterion holds in
604 high-elevation site but not in low elevation site for the
605 germination success. For the time to germination, as
606 expected, plants originating from low-elevation habitats
607 germinated significantly earlier than plants originating
608 from high-elevation habitats in the low-elevation site
609 under light condition (Fig 2 c). In the high-elevation site
610 under light, plant from high-elevation habitat germinated
611 later than plants from low-elevation habitats (Fig 2 c).
612 In the subspecies *A. m. pseudomajus*, the “local vs. foreign
613 elevation” criterion was never satisfied, reflecting the lack
614 of local adaptation for both germination-related traits.
615 Indeed, the populations originating from high-elevation
616 habitats never outperformed the populations originating
617 from low-elevation habitats in the high-elevation garden,
618 and vice-versa (Fig 3).

620 **Adaptive evolutionary responses disturbed by shade.**

621 Patterns of responses to elevation observed under light
622 vanished or reversed under shade in both subspecies (Fig
623 2 and 3 b and d). In particular, the signature of the
624 response to elevation appeared « maladaptive » when
625 assessed under shade in high elevation garden for *A.*
626 *m. striatum*. The significant effects of the three-way
627 interaction elevation of origin \times site elevation \times shade
628 treatment and the two-way interaction site elevation \times
629 shade treatment on germination related-traits showed
630 that signature patterns used to interpret evolutionary
631 signatures of adaptation to elevation were different under
632 light and under shade (Table 3). In the high-elevation
633 site and under light, *A. m. striatum* plants from
634 high-elevation populations had a significantly higher
635 germination rate and a delayed germination compared
636 to plants originating from low-elevation populations.
637 Under shade, we obtained contrasted results in the

Table 1. Results from the generalized mixed models for germination-related traits for both subspecies of *Anthirrinum majus*. Marginal R^2 is the part of variance explained by fixed effects. Conditional R^2 is the part of variance explained by both fixed and random effects.

	<i>A. majus striatum</i>			<i>A. majus pseudomajus</i>		
a) Germination rate (binomial)	Marginal $R^2 = 0.10$, Conditional $R^2 = 0.21$			Marginal $R^2 = 0.12$, Conditional $R^2 = 0.26$		
Fixed effects	Estimates	CI 95% lower	CI 95% upper	Estimates	CI 95% lower	CI 95% upper
<i>Environmental effects</i>						
Intercept	-0.77	-1.12	-0.42	-0.98	-1.24	-0.72
Site elevation (low)	-1.62	-2.15	-1.09	-1.7	-2.1	-1.3
Shade treatment (shade)	-0.18	-0.67	0.3	0.21	-0.12	0.54
Site elevation x Shade (low x shade)	0.89	0.16	1.62	0.9	0.38	1.43
Random effects	Variance	CI 95 % lower	CI 95% upper	Variance	CI 95% lower	CI 95% upper
<i>Genetic effects</i>						
Between populations (V_B)	0	0	Inf	0.07	0	23.57
Family nested in populations (V_F)	0.33	0.17	0.63	0.53	0.38	0.75
<i>G x E effects</i>						
Population x Site elevation x Shade ($V_{B \times E}$)	0.37	0.24	0.58	0.18	0.06	0.55
Family x Site elevation x Shade ($V_{F \times E}$)	0.47	0.29	0.77	0.54	0.36	0.8
b) Time to germination (gaussian)	Marginal $R^2 = 0.19$, Conditional $R^2 = 0.22$			Marginal $R^2 = 0.21$, Conditional $R^2 = 0.45$		
Fixed effects	Estimates	CI 95% lower	CI 95% upper	Estimates	CI 95% lower	CI 95% upper
<i>Environmental effects</i>						
Intercept	31.96	29.58	34.33	30.46	28.76	32.15
Site elevation (low)	-15.61	-19.26	-11.95	-16	-19.23	-12.77
Shade treatment (shade)	-6.41	-9.35	-3.46	-6.43	-8.7	-4.17
Site elevation x Shade (low x shade)	11.3	6.37	16.23	10.44	6.37	14.52
Random effects	Variance	CI 95 % lower	CI 95% upper	Variance	CI 95% lower	CI 95% upper
<i>Genetic effects</i>						
Between populations (V_B)	1.55	0.43	5.58	0	0	Inf
Family nested in populations (V_F)	2.52	1.08	5.88	2.68	1.39	5.16
<i>G x E effects</i>						
Population x Site elevation x Shade ($V_{B \times E}$)	1.66	0.61	4.53	0	0	Inf
Family x Site elevation x Shade ($V_{F \times E}$)	3.2	1.53	6.66	5.14	4.02	6.57

high-elevation site; plants from high-elevation populations had lower germination rates and a similar time to germination compared to plants from low-elevation populations (Fig 2 b and d). In the low-elevation site and under light, plants from low-elevation populations had similar germination rates and germinated earlier than plants from high-elevation populations but there were no significant differences under shade (Fig 2 b and d).

4. Discussion

Our findings illustrate how the experimental simplification of environments that are complex in nature can bias our interpretation of local adaptation and adaptive plasticity. In open light conditions, we found partial evidence suggesting local adaptation to elevation in *A. m. striatum*, but not in *A. m. pseudomajus* by analysing germination-related traits from multiple populations. The signature of an adaptive response to elevation or its lack thereof observed under open light

conditions differed when assessed under shade. Under shade, this signature appeared to be non-adaptive or maladaptive. This finding has two implications for snapdragon plants. First, contrasted results between the open habitat and understory conditions suggest varying selection on germination traits inside populations where the vegetation cover is heterogeneous, which is the case for most if not all snapdragon populations in the wild. Second, our ability to extrapolate adaptation in *A. majus* presents a number of complications resulting from the multidimensional complexity of the environment. Our findings corroborate the recent awareness on this issue in the scientific literature (Morel-Journel *et al.*, 2020). This issue has the potential to challenge our ability to understand adaptive responses to contrasted climate conditions.

Partial signs of local adaptation to elevation detected in open habitat. We found divergence in the genetic variation underlying the germination rate and the time to germination which is likely to be adaptive

Fig. 2. Reaction norms of germination-related traits (mean values \pm 95% CI) for seven populations of *Anthrimum majus striatum* in the two sites (low and high elevation) and under two treatments (open light and understory shade). plots a) and b) refer to germination rate, c) and d) to time to germination, a) and c) refer to light treatment, b) and d) to shade treatment. Significant differences are indicated by asterisks. ***: p.value \leq 0.001, **: 0.001 < p.value \leq 0.01, *: 0.01 < p.value \leq 0.05, !: 0.05 < p.value < 0.1, 'ns': p.value \geq 0.1.

677 for *A. m. striatum*. For the germination rate, partial
 678 evidence of local adaptation to elevation was found in
 679 the high-elevation site, but none was detected in the
 680 low-elevation site. In the high-elevation site, populations
 681 of *A. m. striatum* from high-elevation habitats had higher
 682 germination rates compared to populations from low
 683 elevation habitats, whereas in the low-elevation garden
 684 we found no differences in germination rates between
 685 populations from high- and low-elevation habitats. This
 686 pattern does not on its own provide convincing evidence
 687 for the local adaptation of populations to elevation,
 688 first because it is a partial pattern and second because
 689 the site and elevation effects were confounded in our
 690 experiment. However, it still suggests an imprint of
 691 natural selection imposed by the local conditions in
 692 high-elevation habitats. Climatic conditions in low
 693 elevation gardens were particularly hot and dry in

southern France on that year. It is also possible that the
 signature of local adaptation was masked by experimental
 artefact (Kawecki & Ebert, 2004). Harsh summer
 conditions at low-elevation might have homogenised
 seed responses, with all populations suffering lower
 germination rates than in higher-elevation gardens. This
 pattern invites follow-up studies to replicate the detection
 of the signature of adaptation to elevation on germination.

Our results for the time to germination were consistent
 with our expectations. In the low-elevation site, *A. m.*
striatum populations from low-elevation germinated
 earlier than populations from high-elevation. This result
 is coherent with selection toward earlier germination
 at low elevation that is acknowledged to increase
 fecundity and/or to decrease summer drought mortality
 (Leger *et al.*, 2009). In the high-elevation site, *A.*

Fig. 3. Reaction norms of germination-related traits (mean values \pm 95% CI) for eight populations of *Anthrimum majus pseudomajus* in the two sites (low and high elevation) and under two treatments (light and shade). The legend is identical to Fig 2.

711 *m. striatum* populations from high-elevation showed
 712 delayed germination compared to populations from
 713 low-elevation. The delayed germination of seeds might
 714 be interpreted as a way to reduce the risk of mortality if
 715 unfavourable conditions were to occur at the beginning
 716 of spring (Donohue *et al.*, 2010; Hoyle *et al.*, 2015).
 717 However, the opposite hypothesis, i.e., the benefits of
 718 earlier germination at high elevation also exists in the
 719 literature (Schütz, 2002), although it is more suitable for
 720 annual plants. We have no evidence that this pattern
 721 of delayed germination in the high-elevation gardens
 722 will be advantageous to seedlings or to later adult life
 723 stages. Our results on the time to germination can
 724 therefore only be interpreted as partial evidence of local
 725 adaptation which is based on results in the low-elevation
 726 site. Knowledge on the fitness landscape for the time to
 727 germination in different environments - in particular at
 728 high-elevation site - and the replication of the experiment
 729 in another site at a similar elevation would be required

to obtain a stronger evidence.

The findings described above show that *A. m. striatum* populations from high and low-elevation habitats have genetically diverged in terms of germination rate and time to germination. Considered altogether, these results offer a pattern consistent with local adaptation to elevation (Kawecki & Ebert, 2004). Populations originating from high-elevation habitats outperformed the populations originating from low-elevation habitats in the high-elevation site via higher germination rates whereas the populations originating from low-elevation habitats outperformed the populations originating from high-elevation habitats in the low-elevation site via delayed germination. In contrast, we found no evidence for a pattern of local adaptation to elevation in *A. m. pseudomajus*. These results are consistent with a previous study on *A. majus* that used a $Q_{ST} - F_{ST}$ indirect approach (Marin *et al.*, 2020). They detected

Table 2. Results of the log likelihood ratio test (LRT) performed on the generalized mixed models for germination-related traits for both subspecies of *Antirrhinum majus*. See models estimates in Table 1 and 3.

	LRT	p-value	Df
a) With and without environmental effects			
Germination rates			
<i>A. majus. striatum</i>	28	<0.0001	3
<i>A. majus. pseudomajus</i>	50	<0.0001	3
Time to germination			
<i>A. majus. striatum</i>	38	<0.0001	3
<i>A. majus. pseudomajus</i>	60	<0.0001	3
b) With and without elevation of origin			
Germination rates			
<i>A. majus. striatum</i>	30	<0.0001	4
<i>A. majus. pseudomajus</i>	19	0.0006	4
Time to germination			
<i>A. majus. striatum</i>	10	0.0496	4
<i>A. majus. pseudomajus</i>	13	0.0136	4

a potential signal of local adaptation to elevation on biomass-related traits in *A. m. striatum* but not in *A. m. pseudomajus*. These findings provided us with a suite of signature patterns potentially reflecting local adaptation to elevation. These patterns were different between these two genetically closely related subspecies that harbour different flower colours but share the same ecological range. These patterns suggest that adaptive mechanisms related to elevation might be contributing to the divergence of these subspecies.

Sensitivity of elevation adaptation signature patterns to shade. In *A. m. striatum*, we found that signature patterns reflecting the adaptation of populations to elevation under light were disturbed by shade. Under shade, our results reflected local maladaptation to elevation in germination-related traits. Contrary to expectation, the effect of elevation under shade could not be inferred from simply scaling down the observed patterns under light, i.e., lower germination rate and delayed germination. Examples of empirical studies testing the stability of plant adaptive responses to complexity of the environment are rare (Chevin & Lande, 2015; Westneat *et al.*, 2019). In a recent article, Anderson & Wadgyman (2019) found evidence of local adaptation to elevation in *Boechera stricta* but this pattern was disturbed by changes in snow cover that lead to observe signs of local maladaptation. Neglecting the multivariate nature of the environment may therefore lead to incorrect assessments of how species adapt to their current habitat, and how they will respond to climate changes.

The limits of forecasting responses to climate change on the basis of experimental approaches. Signature

patterns found in classical open habitat conditions might imply that *A. majus* successfully evolved adaptations to climate differences. The range of climate conditions in these mountains is already changing and set to change even more because of climate change. Conditions at high elevation are becoming more similar to conditions from lower elevation (Urli *et al.*, 2014). In this regard, it is encouraging in terms of resilience that *A. majus* seeds originating from high elevation germinated as well as seeds from low elevation at low elevation. One might speculate that seeds will keep germinating at a comfortable rate as hotter temperatures hit higher elevations. However, caution must be exercised with this type of predictions derived from oversimplified experimental approaches. Understory shade conditions can modify the signature of local adaptation, which can alter climate change scenarios.

5. Conclusion

The replication in understory shade of our experiment revealed the lack of stability of plant adaptation signatures detected in common gardens usually conducted in full-light conditions. Our findings also imply that forecasting the ability of plants to adapt to environmental changes based on common garden and reciprocal transplant experiments must account for the multivariate nature of the environment.

6. Author contributions

BP designed the research program. SM, JA, MI, GO, AlG and BP carried out the experiments; AG analysed the data; AG and BP wrote the manuscript.

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8. Conflict of interest disclosure

The authors of this article declare that they have no financial conflict of interest with the content of this article. Benoit Pujol is one of the *PCIEvolBiol* recommenders.

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Table 3. Results from the generalized mixed models (GLMM) testing for local adaptation on germination-related traits in both subspecies of *Antirrhinum majus*. Random factors in all models are the population and the family effects. Marginal R^2 is the part of variance explained by fixed effects. Conditional R^2 is the part of variance explained by both fixed and random effects.

	<i>A. majus striatum</i>			<i>A. majus pseudomajus</i>		
a) Germination rate (binomial)	Marginal $R^2 = 0.12$, Conditional $R^2 = 0.17$			Marginal $R^2 = 0.13$, Conditional $R^2 = 0.22$		
Fixed effects	Estimates	CI 95% lower	CI 95% upper	Estimates	CI 95% lower	CI 95% upper
Intercept	-0.54	-0.87	-0.21	-0.93	-1.23	-0.62
Site elevation (low)	-1.63	-2.03	-1.22	-1.75	-2.21	-1.29
Elevation of origin (low)	-0.46	-0.97	0.05	-0.01	-0.44	0.42
Shade treatment (shade)	-0.71	-1.05	-0.37	-0.15	-0.48	0.19
Elevation of origin (low) x Site elevation (low)	0.07	-0.59	0.74	0.2	-0.44	0.84
Site elevation (low) x Shade (shade)	1.32	0.77	1.87	1.53	0.95	2.11
Elevation of origin (low) x Shade (shade)	1.27	0.77	1.77	0.67	0.21	1.14
Elevation of origin (low) x Site elevation (low) x Shade (shade)	-1.09	-1.95	-0.22	-1.27	-2.08	-0.46
b) Time to germination (gaussian)	Marginal $R^2 = 0.21$, Conditional $R^2 = 0.30$			Marginal $R^2 = 0.22$, Conditional $R^2 = 0.33$		
Fixed effects	Estimates	CI 95% lower	CI 95% upper	Estimates	CI 95% lower	CI 95% upper
Intercept	34.13	31.52	36.74	27.82	25.66	29.98
Site elevation (low)	-16.13	-19.9	-12.36	-13.09	-17.29	-8.89
Elevation of origin (low)	-5	-9.15	-0.85	4.97	1.92	8.01
Shade treatment (shade)	-8.41	-11.39	-5.43	-2.95	-5.7	-0.21
Elevation of origin (low) x Site elevation (low)	0.65	-5.8	7.1	-5.36	-11.19	0.47
Site elevation (low) x Shade (shade)	10.96	5.7	16.21	6.37	1.25	11.49
Elevation of origin (low) x Shade (shade)	4.34	-0.01	8.68	-6	-9.71	-2.3
Elevation of origin (low) x Site elevation (low) x Shade (shade)	1.77	-6.6	10.14	7.34	0.17	14.52

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